

TEXTILE REINFORCED MULTI-LAYER COMPOSITE TUBES FOR PRESSURE LINE SYSTEMS

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SUMMARY: Composite tubes comprised of a plastic core and a textile reinforced concrete coating offer many advantages compared to conventional tube materials. The inner plastic tube, highly resistant against incrustation and aggressive substances provides a sealing function and transports the medium; the outer coating of the concrete tube resists both inner and outer pressure. The positive properties of the comprising materials are ideally combined and compensate for their disadvantages. The reinforcing textiles are bi-axial multi-ply manufactured on Malimo stitch-bonding machines. They have been machine coated to ensure maximum fibre strength and good processing properties. The addition of short fibres to the concrete further improves their excellent load bearing capacity in the composite tubes.

KEYWORDS: textile reinforced concrete, composite tubes, stitch-bonding, Malimo, multi-ply, coating

TEXTILE REINFORCED CONCRETE

Textile reinforced concrete can be applied as a substitute to or in combination with conventional building materials such as steel or short fibre reinforced concrete. It is suited for the production of new components in precast concrete plants as well as for repairing and strengthening existing buildings on site. The textile reinforcing material is inserted into the concrete in the form of long fibres in accordance with the expected load. The usage of long fibres is efficient only when combined with modern textile manufacturing processes due to the large number of possible applications. During the textile processing as well as in the concrete component, it is necessary to maintain the advantageous properties of the high performance filaments. The main advantage of textile reinforcements for concrete is their ability to allow extremely thin-walled parts and thin reinforcing layers. The resulting reduction in mass offers new possibilities for construction and design of concrete components.

Textile reinforced concrete is a composite made of fine grain concrete and high performance filament yarns such as alkali-resistant glass or carbon [1]. The filament yarns are set in concrete in the form of textile grid structures between thin layers of a cementitious medium. Whereas the concrete transmits compression loads, the textile reinforcement carries all occurring tensile forces. An increased load capacity is achieved when the fibres reach about 1 % of the total component volume.

REQUIREMENTS

Reinforcing textiles should be both open and non-deformable. The openness is necessary to guarantee a complete envelopment of the yarn, thus ensuring the transference of the load into the reinforcing component. The form of the textile depends on the maximum grain size, the necessary volumetric content of the fibres and the parameters of the textile machine. The shape accuracy (depending on bending and displacement behaviour) is essential for maximum fibre strength utilization and good handling qualities. The latter is more important on the construction site than in a precast component factory.

Flat multi-ply fabrics manufactured on stitch-bonding machines are especially suitable for the production of textile reinforcements. The main advantages are high productivity, particularly when producing large quantities, and the ideal orientation of the reinforcing layers. Ideal orientation signifies that the threads can be flexibly arranged and drawn in the direction of the expected load. Multi-ply fabrics consist of one or more parallel or drawn layers of threads that can have different directions [2]. Two layers form a bi-axial multi-ply, three or more layers a multi-axial multi-ply fabric.

PRODUCTION OF SUITABLE REINFORCING TEXTILES

At the ITB two machines by KARL MAYER Malimo are used for the production of stitch-bonded fabrics: a multi-axial knitting machine Malimo 14024 (Fig. 1) and a stitch-bonding machine Malimo 14022/c P2-2S with parallel weft insertion. These machines differ in the number and direction of the reinforcing thread systems, the process of inserting the weft threads, the stitching process and the angles that can be realized. On the multi-axial machine, multi-ply fabrics can be produced with four reinforcing layer systems. The laying angles of 0° (work flow direction) and 90° are fixed. The other thread systems can be arranged at any angle between $\pm 45^\circ$ and 90° (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1 – multi-axial warp knitting machine Malimo 14024 (1 - knitting position, 2 - thread regulation system ($+45^\circ$), 3 - weft insertion system (-45°), 4 - weft insertion system (90°), 5 - warp thread guidance)

Fig. 2. – stitch-bonded multi-axial multi-ply

High demands are made on the textile machinery for the production of textile concrete reinforcements:

- The sensitive high performance filament yarns must be treated with care.
- The direction and arrangement of the yarns must be completely maintained in the textile structure and the composite.
- The strength of the filaments should be optimally utilized by creating a composite between the filaments in the yarn.

The stitch-bonding machines at the ITB have been thoroughly modified to suit these demands. The yarn feeding on both machines and the multi-ply transportation system (Malimo 14024) have been improved and supplementary coating and drying devices have been integrated in the multi-axial warp knitting machine (Fig. 3). With these, the multi-ply can be additionally stabilised. The coating is done on full machine speed in the level of the transport system while the multi-ply is still clamped to avoid displacement and relaxation. Thereby, the handling properties, which are important for the work on the construction site, are improved and the tensile strength is very much increased. By applying these measures reinforcing textiles can be manufactured that are well adapted to various usages.

Fig. 3. – coating and drying devices (6 - roll coater, 7 - infrared drying device)

PLASTIC TEXTILE CONCRETE TUBES

In the water and gas industry the past few decades have seen other pipe materials such as steel, stoneware and concrete replaced to a large extent by plastic tubes due to their excellent properties and low costs. However, their limited strength excludes these tubes from different fields of application. This is mainly due to time- and temperature-dependent stress-strain-behaviour, and their low resistance to impact pressure and cracking.

To expand the fields of application, it is necessary to either use more material or add additional reinforcements. Available large diameter plastic tubes for high pressures (inner pressure up to 100 bar) consist of several layers and reinforcements. These are either steel structures or high-performance fibres in cross-wise arrangement. These tubes are manufactured by winding the reinforcement around standardized PE-tubes and coating them with an additional plastic layer. The production of such tubes is very expensive and complex and used only for special cases.

Tubes made of concrete are still regarded as cost-effective and robust. But due to production processes and occurring short cracks, comparatively thick-walled and heavy tubes must be constructed that also limit the number of possible applications.

A new type of tube was created by combining plastic tubes with high-strength textile reinforced concrete coatings (Fig. 4). The tubes developed at the TU Dresden combine the

advantages of both materials. Both the plastic and the concrete tube can be made thinner and bear higher loads. Thus, the costs are distinctly reduced while the properties of the tubes are highly improved. These tubes will find use in areas that have been reserved up to now for steel or cast iron tubes. How the composite tube works is simple. The inner plastic tube transports the fluid and acts as a seal. It has good hydraulic properties and is highly resistant to many media, corrosion and incrustation. Since its function is reduced to lining the concrete, the wall thickness of the expensive plastic tube can be minimized. All loads from inner and outer pressure are carried by the covering tube of textile reinforced concrete. Thus, it is possible to produce completely sealed high strength tubes. A wall thickness of only 10 to 20 mm is sufficient for inner tube diameters of up to 130 mm and inner pressures of 27 to 57 bar.

Fig. 4 – textile reinforced multi-layer tube

The cost-efficient coating consists of open grid textiles made of alkali-resistant glass filament yarns that are laid into a fine grain concrete matrix. The concrete has a large proportion of adhesive cement and a maximum grain size of 2 mm in a winding process (Fig. 5). The textile reinforcements were developed on the basis of the stitch-bonding technology with parallel weft insertion.

Fig. 5 – inserting the textile layer

Several bi-axial reinforcing structures made of alkali-resistant glass filaments have been examined for their processing properties and strength. They differed in aperture size between the reinforcing threads and the amount of reinforcing material. The development of these bi-axial structures was based on the analysis of basic loading cases, the determination of the main load direction and the possible deflection of the reinforcing threads. The dimensioning was kept constant and resulted from empirical knowledge obtained during extensive fundamental research in previous projects. The addition of short fibres to a specially modified concrete had a very positive effect. Particularly under inner pressure the short fibres result in an extension of the linear-elastic region. The collapse load is simultaneously increased to

more than 25 bar (inner diameter 130 mm, wall thickness 12 mm, one yarn of 640 tex in axial direction, two yarns of 640 tex with a distance of 7.2 mm in tangential direction).

A pilot machine has been installed at the TU Dresden to fabricate straight composite tube segments (Fig. 6). On this machine, tubes can be produced up to 1000 mm in length, with an 180 mm outer diameter and variable concrete covers between 10 and 20 mm. The winding technology developed especially for this purpose permits the application of the concrete, the insertion of the textile reinforcement, the calibration of the walls and the smoothing of the surface with a consistent and high quality.

Fig. 6 – experimental rig

TESTING THE PRESSURE RESISTANCE

After 28 days of controlled atmosphere storage, the tube specimen can be used for inner and apex pressure tests. These tests are carried out on testing machines for apex pressure (Fig. 7) and specially developed machines for the measurement of elongation under inner pressure (Fig. 8). The data is collected by highly precise displacement transducers and strain gauges and recorded with a computer. These methods create a large experimental database for the evaluation of composite tubes.

Fig. 7 – apex pressure test

Fig. 8 – inner pressure test

The tests show that the extensional stiffness of the tubes increases considerably with a volumetric content of the reinforcing textile between 1 % and 4 % and of short fibres up to 0.85 %. Depending on the amount of the reinforcing material and the thickness of the concrete layer, inner pressures of up to 40 bar and apex pressures of up to 120 kN/m can be achieved under short-time stress. The deformation compared to standard plastic tubes is greatly reduced.

CONCLUSION

The advantages of textile reinforcements for concrete are clearly visible when applied in composite tubes. The positive properties of the applied materials are combined ideally and compensate for the respective disadvantages. That way it is possible to reduce the amount of material that is necessary for both the inner plastic tube and the concrete coating while the load bearing capacity of the sealed tubes is greatly improved.

The new composite tubes will be applied under and without pressure for supply and disposal purposes. At the moment, the research activities are focused on the transfer of the research results into a pilot application in urban areas or industrial complexes with operating pressures between 0 and 16 bar. For this purpose it is necessary to develop fastening elements, the first of which would be for joining two tubes in a straight-line. The next step will be the development of formed tube parts with practical fastening elements and a production method for long-distance pipelines.

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